

15 **ABSTRACT**

16 Hydrogen- and carbon-bearing aluminosilicate scapolite near the calcium end-
17 member (Me₇₂) is investigated via in situ high-pressure Raman spectroscopy and via
18 high-temperature Raman combined with mid-infrared spectroscopy, up to 18.1 GPa and
19 700 °C, respectively. Experimental results show the following main findings. (1) Abrupt
20 decrease in overall Raman intensity, together with the disappearance of ring-structure
21 peaks, indicates a phase transition between 10 and 12 GPa, consistent with the reported
22 pressure of the tetragonal-to-triclinic transformation. (2) Crystal amorphization occurs
23 at ~18 GPa in the analyzed composition, as evidenced by broad weak bands attributed
24 to AlO₄ and SiO₄ tetrahedra. A newly emerged peak at ~990 cm⁻¹ observed at 16 GPa
25 may mark the onset of such process. (3) Clear signals and a continuous blueshift in the
26 CO₃²⁻ peak position over the entire pressure range indicate the high-pressure stability
27 of carbon at the cage site. (4) Upon heating, the framework Raman peaks exhibit
28 negligible changes. For CO₃²⁻, both the shifts of the fundamental Raman modes and the
29 integrated infrared absorbance of its combination bands remain reversible, confirming
30 thermal stability reaching 700 °C. At 200 °C, band splitting of the carbonate asymmetric
31 overtone and combination bands near 3000 cm⁻¹ suggests disordered arrangement of
32 cage clusters. (5) In contrast, the structural hydrogen, present as hydroxyl groups, is
33 relatively sensitive to heat. An infrared redshift is observed at high temperature, and
34 approximately 50% of the hydrogen is released during the heating experiment. The
35 hydrogen emission point is inferred to be above 500 °C. Scapolite-group minerals have
36 been regarded as important reservoirs of carbon and sulfur in Earth's crust. Combining

37 our single-crystal mineral physics evidences with previous synthesis experiments, we
38 suggest that silicate scapolite in low water fugacity systems may potentially transport
39 carbon stored in structural cages into the upper mantle via cold subduction.

40 **KEYWORDS:** scapolite, hydrogen, carbon, subduction, Raman, infrared

41

42 **INTRODUCTION**

43 The interior cycling of volatiles, exemplified by hydrogen (H) and carbon (C),
44 underpins Earth's deep evolution and surface habitability by affecting fundamental
45 processes including plate tectonics, volcanic activity, atmospheric composition, and life
46 emergence.¹⁻⁴ The surface ocean and atmosphere, largely composed of these elements,
47 likely originated from early mantle degassing.⁵ In turn, volatiles are recycled into the
48 lithosphere and deeper mantle through subduction zones,⁶ where they are hosted in the
49 lattices of specific minerals. An intriguing question concerns the forms and
50 transformations of such host phases, as well as their reactions under high-pressure and
51 high-temperature conditions. For instance, it has been shown that, serpentine and its
52 high-pressure counterpart, dense hydrous magnesium silicates, act as effective
53 hydrogen carriers at different depths, from the upper mantle to the mantle transition
54 zone and possibly into the lower mantle, containing water (a form of H) at one to over
55 ten weight percent level.⁷ On the other hand, the subducting carbon flux is primarily
56 hosted by Ca–Mg carbonate phases (e.g., calcite, aragonite, dolomite, and magnesite),
57 which remain stable to significant depths before prospective transformation to
58 diamond.⁸ Considerable efforts have been devoted to identifying potential candidates.

59 Scapolite, a family of open-framework aluminosilicates, is capable of
60 accommodating volatile components (e.g., F^- , Cl^- , OH^- , HCO_3^- , HSO_4^- , CO_3^{2-} , SO_4^{2-} ,
61 HCl , H_2O) within structural voids at several weight percent.⁹⁻¹² More importantly,
62 synthesis experiments have revealed that it can form and remain stable under pressure–
63 temperature conditions spanning the crust to the shallow upper mantle, depending on
64 system composition and fluid availability,¹³⁻¹⁹ and it has also been discovered in
65 xenoliths and a wide range of lower crustal rock types.²⁰⁻²³ Hence, in many studies, the
66 mineral is proposed to be a significant budget of carbon and sulfur (S) in the crust and
67 possibly the lithospheric mantle, and to influence deep volatile transfer.^{13,23-27} A recent
68 estimate based on mass and volume fractions points out that approximately 10% of the
69 total sulfur in the lower continental crust is hosted by scapolite, while the associated
70 carbon is about half that of sulfur, at around 10^{20} grams.²³ In nature, scapolite-group
71 minerals are widespread as rock-forming or accessory phases in hydrothermal,
72 metasomatic, and metamorphic terranes, and also occur in some igneous rocks.
73 Extraterrestrial occurrences have been founded in an LL3 chondrite and in a melt
74 inclusion from the Martian meteorite Nakhla.^{28,29} The mineral's general chemical
75 formula can be expressed as $M_4T_{12}O_{24}A$, where M represents monovalent and divalent
76 metallic elements, mainly Na, Ca (with minor K, Fe, Sr, and Ba), T stands for trivalent
77 and tetravalent elements like Al and Si (rarely Fe), and A is the anions and anionic
78 groups mentioned above. And its composition can, in fact, be considered as a salt-
79 bearing analogue of feldspar, namely three plagioclase units plus one salt component.
80 Most natural scapolite solid solutions lie between three recognized end-members:

81 $\text{Na}_4\text{Al}_3\text{Si}_9\text{O}_{24}\text{Cl}$ (marialite), $\text{Ca}_4\text{Al}_6\text{Si}_6\text{O}_{24}\text{CO}_3$ (meionite), and $\text{Ca}_4\text{Al}_6\text{Si}_6\text{O}_{24}\text{SO}_4$
82 (silvialite);^{9,10,30} it is common practice to use the meionite percentage as a composition
83 index, Me_X , where $X = \Sigma(\text{M}^{2+}) / \Sigma(\text{M}^+ + \text{M}^{2+})$. From a crystallographic perspective,
84 scapolite is a microporous tectosilicate similar to zeolites and other feldspathoids. Its
85 crystal structure is characterized by oval-shaped channels for M sites and larger cages
86 for A sites, formed from linked four-membered rings of $\text{AlO}_4/\text{SiO}_4$ tetrahedra. Two
87 types of rings exist, which accordingly define three tetrahedral sites: T1 and T2 in space
88 group $I4/m$, and T1, T2, and T3 (split from T2) in the lower-symmetry $P4_2/n$ structure.
89 Specifically, and of interest in this investigation, each anion occupies a “cage site”
90 coordinated by four Na/K/Ca cations in a square-planar geometry, thus forming a cage
91 cluster, and is located between successive T1 rings.

92 Existing studies addressing the pressure and thermal stability of carbon and, in
93 particular, hydrogen in scapolite are relatively limited. Early pioneering work
94 combining thermal analysis (thermogravimetry, TG, and differential thermal analysis,
95 DTA) with mass spectrometry indicates a five-step volatile emission sequence
96 involving H_2O , SO_2 , CO_2 , NaCl , and KCl up to 800 °C. The release of H_2O and CO_2
97 begins at around 100 °C across different compositions, whereas sulfur exhibits higher
98 retention up to ~300 °C.³¹ The work also shows that a second major H_2O mass-loss
99 event occurs at 150–250 °C, and that a positive correlation exists between $\text{CO}_2 + \text{SO}_2$
100 release and meionite content. By contrast, a later study obtains quite a different result.
101 Using sensitive differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), together with TG and DTA
102 analyses of Me_{33} and Me_{80} , it shows that CO_2 , SO_2 , and NaCl are not released until

1100–1200 °C.³² The DSC curve indicates an ordering-to-disordering transition of the
[M₄A] cage clusters in Me₃₃ at 300 °C. In scapolite with >75% meionite, such clusters
remain disordered across both ambient and elevated temperatures.^{32,33} High-pressure
behavior of CO₃²⁻ in Me₃₆ is reported by a more recent research using synchrotron X-
ray diffraction and vibrational spectroscopy.³⁴ Raman and infrared carbonate peak shifts
exhibit a sharp discontinuity at ~10.7–10.8 GPa, consistent with the tetragonal-to-
triclinic phase transition, reflecting a mutation in bond length. The anomalous negative
pressure dependence of Raman peak positions in the triclinic phase is interpreted to
reflect compression and elongation of CO₃²⁻ groups by the four-membered ring.
Another controversy concerns the presence of hydrogen. Some studies explain that it is
virtually not incorporated into the scapolite structure, which in turn allows the Cl or
CO₂ content of the formation environment to be traced.^{28,35–37} A previous systematic
review, however, has emphasized its significance, showing that anhydrous scapolite is
actually uncommon (≤5% of analyzed cases), and that a number of samples contain H
at levels exceeding 0.1 and even 0.4 atoms per formula unit.³⁸ This element tends to
occur in the form of monovalent anions such as OH⁻, HCO₃⁻, HSO₄⁻, and possibly as
molecular H₂O. In this context, we report a carbon- and hydrogen-bearing Me₇₂
scapolite and explore its in situ vibrational spectroscopic features under non-ambient
pressure and temperature.

122

123 **METHODS**

124 Natural scapolite grains are separated from high-pressure granulite sampled in the

125 Namche Barwa area of the Eastern Himalayan Syntaxis. The host rock is characterized
126 by high carbon content, and its petrographic features include scapolite occurring in
127 association with diopside, quartz, titanite, and wollastonite (Figure S1).

128 Chemical composition of the mineral is determined using a JEOL JXA-8900
129 electron microprobe at the Institute of Geology, Chinese Academy of Geological
130 Sciences, operating at 15 kV accelerating voltage, 20 nA beam current, a 5 μm spot size,
131 and a counting time of 10 s. Results from multiple analytical spots are averaged. The
132 presence and abundances of C- and H-species are identified and semi-quantified using
133 ambient Raman and infrared spectroscopy.

134 In situ high-pressure Raman spectra are collected during compression and
135 decompression up to 18.1 GPa at ambient temperature. We use a symmetric-type
136 diamond anvil cell equipped with type Ia diamonds with 400- μm culets to compress the
137 crystal. A doubly polished scapolite chip and a ruby fragment are loaded into a 150- μm
138 diameter round sample chamber in a rhenium gasket. The use of neon as the pressure-
139 transmitting medium ensures pressure gradients below 0.15 GPa up to a maximum
140 pressure of 20 GPa.³⁹ Raman spectra are acquired using a WITec alpha 300R confocal
141 Raman microscope with a 20 \times objective at the Center for High Pressure Science and
142 Technology Advanced Research. The radiation is excited by a 532-nm solid-state laser
143 and recorded in the range from 100 to 1200 cm^{-1} . Due to the low intensity of in situ H-
144 related Raman signals, high-frequency region (3000–3800 cm^{-1}) is not measured. Each
145 spectrum is accumulated 5 times with a 10 s exposure time and a spectral resolution of
146 1 cm^{-1} . The laser power is 30 mW. Pressure is calibrated based on the wavelength shift

147 of ruby R1 fluorescence peak.⁴⁰ All grains used here and below are unoriented and are
148 dried at 100 °C in a muffle oven for 1 h prior to measurements.

149 In situ high-temperature Raman and infrared (IR) spectroscopy are performed
150 during heating and cooling up to 700 °C at ambient pressure, in 100 °C steps. Thermal
151 conditions are achieved using a Linkam TS1400 heating stage with a SiO₂ window and
152 a Rh/Pt thermocouple. We set a heating/cooling rate of 10 °C/min, and each temperature
153 point is maintained for 20 min to reach equilibrium. Both Raman and IR spectra are
154 collected at the Institute of Geology and Geophysics, Chinese Academy of Sciences.
155 The same type of Raman microscope is used, with the following experimental
156 parameters: 5 accumulated scans per spectrum, 10 s exposure time, and 25 mW laser
157 power. The Raman wavenumber range is 0–1200 cm⁻¹ with a spectral resolution of 3
158 cm⁻¹. For IR measurements, we use a Bruker INVENIO-R FTIR spectrometer equipped
159 with a HYPERION 1000 microscope, a 20× objective, a CaF₂ beam splitter, and an
160 MCT detector. The spectral range of interest is 2400–4000 cm⁻¹, with each spectrum
161 recorded using a 50 × 50 μm aperture at a resolution of 2 cm⁻¹ and obtained from 128
162 accumulations. Using the microscope crosshair scale, the IR sample thickness is
163 estimated to be 50 μm. Spectral data processing is carried out using the SciPy Python
164 package, including baseline correction (ALS algorithm), smoothing (Savitzky–Golay
165 filter), peak identification (local maxima and second derivatives), and area integration
166 (polygon method).

167

168 **RESULTS**

169 The sample is characterized by electron microprobe analysis as Me_{72} scapolite,
170 containing 2.77 wt.% Na_2O , 1.15 wt.% K_2O , 17.3 wt.% CaO , 47.09 wt.% SiO_2 , 25.86
171 wt.% Al_2O_3 , and 1.08 wt.% Cl , together with minor FeO (0.46 wt.%) and trace amounts
172 of MgO , MnO , TiO_2 , and SO_3 (<0.2 wt.%). According to the ambient transmission
173 infrared spectrum (Figure 3a and results below), both structural OH^- and CO_3^{2-} are
174 identified. Quantitative infrared analysis is based on the modified Beer–Lambert law.
175 For our single IR measurement, the triply integrated absorption coefficient is used as a
176 proxy for the total absorbance.⁴¹ Since there is no specific infrared calibration available
177 for scapolite, we applied the molar absorption coefficient of apatite for carbonate,⁴² and
178 used a frequency-based method for hydroxyl,⁴³ and adopted a density of 2.72 g/cm^3 for
179 Me_{72} . The estimated concentrations are 1.19 wt.% in CO_2 form and 68.04 ppm in H_2O
180 form. Although for one spectrum the uncertainty may be several-fold,⁴¹ the result is
181 generally correct in order of magnitude. In turn, if H is ignored, the CO_2 concentration
182 is calculated to be 4.48 wt.% based on mass balance.

183 Raman spectra and pressure-induced shifts in vibrational modes are shown in
184 Figure 1 and Table S1. At ambient conditions, nine peaks ($\nu_{\text{r}1}$ – $\nu_{\text{r}9}$) are assigned (Fig.
185 1a). Four peaks in the 200 – 400 cm^{-1} range are attributed to the vibration of ring
186 structures,³⁴ located at 205 ($\nu_{\text{r}1}$), 257 ($\nu_{\text{r}2}$), 295 ($\nu_{\text{r}3}$), and 361 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{r}4}$). Two strong
187 peaks at 455 ($\nu_{\text{r}5}$) and 531 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{r}6}$) are due to the symmetric stretches of AlO_4 and
188 SiO_4 , respectively.³⁴ A broad peak at 769 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{r}7}$) may be attributed to framework T–
189 O–T stretching vibrations (mainly Si–O–Al linkages) within the aluminosilicate
190 framework. In addition, a shoulder peak at 1089 cm^{-1} ($\nu_{\text{r}8}$) and a prominent peak at

191 1102 cm^{-1} (ν_{r9}) are observed, corresponding to the symmetric stretching modes of
 192 CO_3^{2-} in distinct Na–K–Ca local environments (note that symmetric stretching
 193 vibrations do not exhibit degeneracy splitting).

194
 195 **Figure 1.** Pressure-dependent Raman features of Me_{72} scapolite. (a) Raman spectrum
 196 at ambient pressure with peak assignments. (b) Raman spectra during compression and
 197 decompression. (c) Evolution of vibrational modes as a function of pressure. Solid and
 198 open squares/bars denote increasing and decreasing pressure, respectively.
 199 Abbreviations: amb. = ambient; tet. = tetragonal; tri. = triclinic; and amorph. =
 200 amorphous.

201 During compression, all peaks shift to higher wavenumbers in response to
 202 increasing pressure (Fig. 1b, c). Below 10 GPa, most peaks shift and broaden without

203 significant changes, indicating generally unchanged structure. Band ν_{r3} splits into two
204 weaker and untraceable bands when the pressure reaches 6.26 GPa. This is possibly
205 caused by subtle modification in the deformation mechanism.⁴⁴ Likewise, the ν_{r2} band
206 undergoes splitting at 8.26 GPa. Marked variations are observed when the pressure
207 increases from 9.5 to 12.07 GPa: (1) all peaks exhibit a sharp decrease in intensity, with
208 ν_{r1} and ν_{r4} being obscured by the background; and (2) peak broadening further increases.
209 These findings point to a structural transition preferentially into triclinic symmetry,
210 consistent with prior experimental observations.^{34,44-46} Next, at the highest pressure
211 point, carbonate peaks dominate the spectrum, while the broad and weak $\text{AlO}_4/\text{SiO}_4$
212 tetrahedral bands indicate that the silicate framework has become highly disordered.
213 The onset of pre-amorphization may be indicated by a newly emerged peak at 987 cm^{-1}
214 (labeled ν_{r10}) at 15.98 GPa.

215 During the decompression early stage, residual peaks continue to exhibit a
216 progressive blueshift and decreasing intensity, and the $\nu_{r5}-\nu_{r7}$ modes cannot be tracked
217 until 11.98 GPa, indicating phase-transition hysteresis. Similar hysteresis has been
218 reported at 6 GPa for synthetic marialite.⁴⁶ The sample reverts to a crystalline state at
219 approximately 12 GPa and returns to the tetragonal phase at 8 GPa, the latter being
220 indicated by the increased overall peak intensity and the reappearance of the ν_{r1} and ν_{r4}
221 peaks. This phase transformation lagged by ~ 1.5 GPa relative to compression. Nearly
222 all peak positions are reversible by the end of the experiment; although their intensities
223 decrease, the peak widths are nearly unchanged.

224 High-temperature Raman spectral patterns are illustrated in [Figure 2](#) and [Table S2](#).

225 The second analyzed grain shows slightly different characteristics, with the absence of
 226 ν_{r1} and the appearance of new bands ν_{r11} and ν_{r12} related to the lattice framework (Fig.
 227 2a). The signal at 964 cm^{-1} (ν_{r13}) suggests of trace SO_4^{2-} .³⁴ Mode ν_{r14} at 1049 cm^{-1}
 228 correspond to CO_3^{2-} in a different local environment.

229
 230 **Figure 2.** Temperature-dependent Raman features of Me_{72} scapolite. (a) Raman
 231 spectrum at ambient temperature with peak assignments. (b) Raman spectra during
 232 heating and cooling. (c) Evolution of vibrational modes as a function of temperature.
 233 Solid and open squares/bars denote increasing and decreasing temperature, respectively.
 234 Abbreviations: amb. = ambient.

235 Throughout the heating and subsequent cooling processes, the scapolite
 236 framework exhibits only reversible shrinkage and contraction, without evidence of

237 lattice breakdown, as indicated by the nearly unchanged peak positions below 900 cm^{-1}
238 (Fig. 2b, c). The sulfate peak fades above $100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, with almost no wavenumber shift.
239 For carbonate, its lower-frequency peak (ν_{r14}) redshifts with increasing temperature,
240 reflecting an elongated average bond length, while the higher-frequency peak (ν_{r9})
241 shows no systematic variation. Within measurement uncertainty, all vibrational modes
242 are reversible, and no obvious intensity changes of volatile-related peaks are observed
243 when normalized to framework peaks.

244 Infrared spectroscopy is more sensitive to volatile species owing to the strong
245 polarity of their chemical bonds. Figure 3 and Table S3 illustrate the mid-infrared
246 patterns at different temperatures. The infrared assignments of scapolite have been
247 systematically studied.^{11,47,12} Here, under ambient conditions, we focus on seven peaks
248 (ν_{i1} – ν_{i7}) within the 2400 – 3800 cm^{-1} (Fig. 3a). Two peaks at 2515 and 2616 cm^{-1} (ν_{i1}
249 and ν_{i3}) are due to combinations of carbonate symmetric and asymmetric stretching
250 modes. This doublet results from lattice-induced symmetry breaking of the planar
251 triangular carbonate anion. A slope anomaly identified by second-derivative analysis at
252 2557 cm^{-1} is attributed to hydrogen bond stretch of minor HCO_3^{2-} (ν_{i2}). Three infrared
253 peaks at, 2852 (ν_{i4}), 2945 (ν_{i5}), and 3035 cm^{-1} (ν_{i6}) are the first overtone and
254 combination bands of carbonate asymmetric stretching modes. The hydroxyl envelope
255 peak at 3643 cm^{-1} indicates slightly distinct local hydrogen environments. We attribute
256 these hydroxyl groups to cage site OH rather than protonated framework oxygen, based
257 on their sharp band shape and relatively high vibrational frequency. And there is no
258 discernible stretching signal attributable to HCO_3^{2-} is detected near 3500 cm^{-1} . Besides,

259 two bands at 3400 and 3730 cm^{-1} are observed. The broad width of the former and the
 260 high frequency of the latter indicate structural disorder and very weak hydrogen
 261 bonding (i.e., nearly free OH). Thus, they are interpreted as molecular water adsorbed
 262 on the surface, most likely originating from residual steam in the heating system. These
 263 signals are unstable and generally fade above 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

264
 265 **Figure 3.** Temperature-dependent infrared features of Me_{72} scapolite. (a) Infrared
 266 spectrum at ambient temperature with peak assignments. (b) Infrared spectra during
 267 heating and cooling. (c) Evolution of vibrational modes as a function of temperature.
 268 Solid and open squares/bars denote increasing and decreasing temperature, respectively.
 269 Abbreviations: amb. = ambient.

270 At elevated temperatures, the positions of ν_{11} and ν_{12} exhibit fluctuations, whereas

271 ν_{13} undergoes a persistent redshift (Fig. 3b, c). Splitting of the overtone and combination
272 bands ν_{14} and ν_{15} at 200 °C may reflect increased structural disorder of carbonate anions
273 within the lattice at elevated temperature. In a previous study, the disordering of anion
274 cage clusters in Me_{33} at 300 °C has been reported.³² Part of this disordering may be
275 irreversible, as the split ν_{14} band does not recover upon cooling. At 400 °C, the merging
276 of ν_{11} – ν_{13} suggests a more symmetric carbonate geometry, likely resulting from lattice
277 thermal expansion. With respect to the OH band, we observe general peak broadening
278 and a shift toward lower wavenumbers during heating, with a blueshift emerging at
279 700 °C. Quantifying water at non-ambient temperatures is challenging due to thermally
280 induced changes in the molar absorptivity. However, the reduction in integrated
281 absorbance after cooling does demonstrate a loss of hydrogen. The carbonate, in
282 contrast, shows better stability with no discernible changed content.

283

284 **DISCUSSION AND IMPLICATION**

285 Crystal-chemically, Me_{72} scapolite undergoes a reversible three-stage phase
286 transition from tetragonal to triclinic, and ultimately to an amorphous state at
287 approximately 10–12 GPa and 16–18 GPa, respectively. The first transition point is in
288 agreement with previous studies, as this phenomenon is reported for Me_{47} at around 9.8
289 GPa,⁴⁴ and subsequently for Me_{36} (~10.7 GPa),³⁴ and for Me_{47} under both high-pressure
290 and high-temperature conditions (~10.5 GPa at 650 °C).⁴⁵ Na end-member marialite is
291 observed to transform at 8.2 GPa.⁴⁶ The Raman spectral features acquired before and
292 after the phase transition deviate from those reported in previous literature (see

293 introduction).³⁴ One plausible interpretation is that the space group in this case deviates
294 from the more commonly reported $P4_2/n$. And interestingly, the amorphization point,
295 which represents the upper pressure stability, is speculated for the first time. The
296 structure remains crystalline up to the previously highest investigated pressure of 18–
297 20 GPa for Me₃₆ and Me₄₇, although spectroscopic evidence for potential amorphization
298 at 17 GPa is noted.³⁴ Experiments have shown that Na–O bonds exhibit higher
299 compressibility than Ca–O bonds.^{26,48} Thus, one possible explanation is that the more
300 rigid Ca–O bonds in our Ca-rich scapolite lead to faster local stress accumulation after
301 the phase transition, and hence partial pressure-induced amorphization at lower
302 pressures than in the Na end-member. In contrast, more compliant Na–O bonds
303 accommodate stress through local bond-angle adjustments, enabling plastic
304 deformation and preserving crystallinity to higher pressures. In terms of thermal
305 stability, the lattice remains stable up to 700 °C, compatible with previous
306 investigations.⁴⁵

307 Carbonate and hydroxyl are the dominant volatile species in this target sample.
308 High-pressure Raman data for CO₃²⁻ indicate that this species remains stably
309 accommodated in the cage site up to the maximum pressure examined. In comparison,
310 a redshift Raman pattern in the triclinic phase,³⁴ previously attributed to anion extrusion
311 by the four-membered rings, is not observed here. Given that four M-site cations occupy
312 each anion site to form cage clusters, such discrepancy may be caused by the difference
313 in ionic radii between Na⁺ and Ca²⁺. Both high-temperature Raman and IR experiments
314 confirm prominent thermal stability of carbonate anions as high as 700 °C. This

315 contradicts the earliest observations of C loss at 100 °C,³¹ but is consistent with later
316 results indicating that C is only released above 1100 °C.³² The carbonate asymmetric
317 overtone and combination bands near 3000 cm⁻¹ are sensitive to site symmetry. Based
318 on the absence of recovery of band ν_{i4} , the peak splitting observed at ~200 °C is unlikely
319 to result from other factors (e.g., anharmonic coupling). Transmission electron
320 microscopy study indicate that our Me₇₂ sample should belong to the ordered cage
321 cluster series.³³ Thus, we conclude that the disordering of [NaCa₃CO₃] and [Ca₄CO₃]
322 clusters initiates at ~200 °C, which is 100 °C lower than that detected by DSC.³²
323 Regarding hydrogen speciation, we assign it primarily to hydroxyl groups at the A-site
324 based on infrared vibrational positions. A reduction of approximately one half (0.46
325 down to 0.24 cm⁻¹) in the integrated infrared absorbance upon cooling the sample to
326 ambient conditions indicates heat-induced hydrogen release. As shown in [Figure 3b](#), a
327 continuous weakening of the OH peak occurs during heating between 500 and 700 °C,
328 accompanied by changes in the peak profile. We therefore infer that emission initiates
329 near 600 °C, but further confirmation is required. It is worth noting that cancrinite,
330 another microporous feldspathoid similar to scapolite, with cages that host molecular
331 H₂O; dehydration experiments and the evolution of unit-cell parameters indicate that
332 water loss occurs around 500 °C.⁴⁹

333 Scapolite has been viewed as a carbon reservoir in the Earth's interior, at least
334 within the crust, and our single-crystal experiments suggest it may extend to greater
335 depths. Ca-rich scapolite tends to stabilize at pressures approaching those of the mantle
336 transition zone, whereas the Na end-member exhibits greater pressure tolerance but

337 generally a lower carbon-carrying capacity. Despite its minor abundance, hydrogen acts
338 as a destabilizing component.^{14,17} The liberation of hydrogen, and thus water, enhances
339 the decomposition of scapolite (e.g., to plagioclase), leading to carbon loss to the
340 environment or transformation of carbon into calcite. Integrating our high-pressure and
341 high-temperature spectral data, we propose that relatively anhydrous scapolite may
342 serve as a deep carbon host, enabling the simultaneous incorporation of carbon and
343 silicon,⁵⁰ and transporting carbon within its structure into the upper mantle via cold
344 subduction. Further in situ experiments on compositionally realistic petrological
345 systems would help explore this proposition.

346

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351

352 **SUPPORTING INFORMATION**

353 Microphotograph of a representative rock thin section ([Figure S1](#)); Raman peak
354 positions of vibrational modes at different pressures and temperatures ([Table S1](#) and
355 [S2](#)); Infrared peak positions of vibrational modes at different temperatures ([Table S3](#)).

356 All the above supplementary materials are combined into a single PDF file.

357

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